

Negative Word Form in Sibling Rivalry: A Psycholinguistic Study

Ahyati Kurniamala Niswariyana¹, I Nengah Sudipa², I Nyoman Suparwa³, I Nyoman Aryawibawa⁴

Article history:

Received June 2023; Accepted: August 02, 2023; Displayed Online: August 26, 2023; Published: December 30, 2023

Keywords

Negative words;
Sibling rivalry;
Psycholinguistics;

Abstract

Sibling rivalry is a spirit of jealousy, competition, or anger between brothers and sisters that starts from the birth of the younger sibling in the family. This research uses a qualitative approach. This research aims to find forms of negative words when sibling rivalry occurs. The theory used to analyze the problem in this research is psycholinguistic. The data source used in this research is sibling language data with an age range of 2-12 years. Meanwhile, the method used in this research is the observation method, using tapping techniques for data collection; the data analysis method uses the intralingua matching method, and the method for presenting the results of data analysis uses informal methods. This research uses a descriptive qualitative approach. The research results found negative words, namely no, and not. Meanwhile, the involvement of negative emotions in sibling rivalry situations includes anger, crying, and screaming.

1. Introduction

Sibling behavior is often an interesting discussion in conversations between parents. Sibling children have a high level of jealousy towards each other, not infrequently words of ownership, anger, wanting to win alone, wanting to be cared for, and wanting to get more portion than their siblings, in many ways will trigger tension between siblings. Parents have a big responsibility in shaping their children's character from childhood. Parents are responsible for providing a comfortable environment for their children. Good communication between parents and children greatly influences the child's personality. The presence of a second child can be associated with a decrease in

¹ Universitas Udayana Denpasar, Denpasar, Indonesia.

the number and positive attitudes of the mother's interactions with her first child. The decrease in interaction between the mother and her first child was caused by the mother having to share her attention with the newborn sibling.

Siblings do not always get along all the time. In the family, it is not uncommon for siblings to compete to be the most dominant; this triggers sibling rivalry, which is called sibling rivalry. In sibling rivalry, negative words such as no, no, don't, negative emotions such as anger, crying, and shouting, and negative actions such as hitting, pinching, slapping, and kicking often arise between siblings. Then, the forms of negative words that appear in sibling rivalry situations are the main problem in this research.

2. Materials and Methods

Dardjowidjojo (2012:7) states that psycholinguistics is a science that studies the mental processes that humans go through when speaking. Sibling rivalry is usually more common if the older and younger siblings have an age gap between 1 and 3 years. Furthermore, sibling rivalry usually appears and is visible when children reach the age of 3 to 6 years, then will occur again at the age of 8 to 12 years. In general, sibling rivalry occurs more often in children of the same gender (Ulia, 2020, p. 13). Ulia further said sibling rivalry is competition or deep jealousy and hatred towards one's own sibling.

Method

The approach used in this study is qualitative. (Bungin, 2001:124) that qualitative research data is expressed in the form of sentences and descriptions and can even be in the form of short stories. It is said to be a listening method because the method used to obtain data is done by listening to the use of language. The term listening here relates to the use of language orally. This method has a basic technique in the form of a tapping technique. (Mahsun, 2005:126). The data analysis method is the intralingual equivalent method by connecting and comparing lingual elements found in one language (Mahsun, 2005, p. 112). This method can be used if the data is available. The method of presenting data in this study uses an informal method, namely the method of presenting data using ordinary words, even though technical terminology cannot be avoided (Sudaryanto, 2015, p. 241).

3. Results and Discussions

Negative Word Forms in Sibling Rivalry

Negative words start with one of: no, no, no (<https://id.m.wikibooks.org>). Below is data on sibling fights in snippets of sibling rivalry events at a house in Mataram. This Sibling Rivalry data was taken using the recording process during an argument between Gigis and Chaca, who were fighting over Barbie's houses.

Sibling fight data

*(GG= Gigis, CC= Chaca, MM= Mother, number (1-42) is the numbering of conversations to facilitate the analysis process).

GG : "Ini apa no, iih." (1) / What is this

CC : "Ini Caca mau jadiin orang." (2) / This is Caca, want to create people

-
- GG : "Ini ngapain dulu?" (3)/ what are you doing
 CC : "Ndak mau!" (4) / I do not want
 GG : "Ndak usah!" (5) / No need
 CC : "Mau main" (sambil menangis). (6) / I want to play (crying)
 GG : "Ndak ndak, ndak usah!" (7) / No, No, No need
 CC : "Mau main" (terus menangis). (8) / I want to play
 GG : "Ndak usah!" (9) / No need
 CC : "Mau main" (menangis). (10) / I want to play (crying)
 MM : "Mau main apa sih sebenarnya?" (11) / What do you exactly want to play
 GG : "Dia maunya tiga rumah, padahal kakak maunya yang itu, masih ada banyak" (menunjuk mainan rumah-rumahan barbie). (12) / He wants three houses, even though his sister wants that one, there are still many" (pointing at barbie toy houses)
 MM : "Caca mau rumah yang mana? Rumah barbie?" (13)/ which one would you like to play Caca? Barbie toy house?
 CC : (crying). (14)
 GG : "Tau gitu kemarin harusnya Caca ikut ngaji biar bisa main, biar hari ini mainnya (main di luar bersama teman-temannya), emm kemarin Caca sudah main sendiri, pakai rumah itu lagi." (15) / You should joined praying yesterday so you could play (playing outside with her friends), but yesterday you played alone with that toy house
 MM : "Rumah yang mana yang diperebutin?" (16)/ Which house is contested?
 GG : "Itu (menunjuk rumah barbie) yang sedang itu." (17) / That one (pointing to Barbie's house)
 CC : (Menangis) "bukan, Caca ndak mau pakai rumah itu." (18)/ No, Caca does not use that toy house
 GG : "Pokoknya ndak mau!" (19)/ I say no!
 CC : "Caca ndak mau pakai rumah itu, Caca cuma berdiriin doang" (Crying). (20)/ Caca does not want using that house. Caca ju make it standing
 GG : "Ndak kakak ndak mau pakai rumah yang lain, pokoknya mau itu!" (21)/ No, I also do not want other toy house. I just want that one.
 CC : "Tapi kakak terus yang pakai rumah itu, Caca ndak pernah" (terus menangis). (22)/ But sister keeps using that house, Caca never use it.
 GG : "Ndak peduli!" (23)/ I do not care
 CC : "Ndak mau Caca kalau kayak gitu, kakak kayak gitu terus (menangis) (24)/ I do not want Caca to be like that, my sister keeps being like that (crying) (24)
 GG : "Ya udah nggak usah main" (25)/ Yeah, no need to play (25)
 CC : "Ndak mau, mau main!" (26)/ No, I want to play!
 GG : "Ii ndak mau." (27)/ I do not want
 CC : "Mau main" (berteriak). (28) / I want to play (screaming)
 GG : "Pokoknya ndak boleh kalau Caca mau rumah itu, ndak boleh." (29)/ Basically, it's not allowed if Caca wants that house, it's not allowed.
 CC : "Mau maiinnn!" (berteriak). (30)/ I wan to play (screaming)
 GG : "Enggak" (nada katus). (31) / No (sound tone)
 CC : "Mau maiinn" (menangis). (32)/ I want to play (cry)
 GG : "Ya udah hari ini Caca boleh main, besok ndak boleh." (33)/ Ok, today Caca can play, tomorrow she does not play.
 CC : "Ndak mauuu (menangis) ndak mau nggak main." (34)/ No, I don't (cry). I do not want if I don't play

- GG : "Ii kan kemarin Caca udah main." (35) / But you have played yesterday
 CC : "Nggak mau nggak main." (36)/). I do not want if I don't play
 GG : "Kemarin Caca udah main, kakak ndak pernah." (37) / Yesterday You did, I never
 CC : "Nggak mau ngak main." (38)/). I do not want if I don't play
 GG : "Ya udah, ndak usah Caca ke kamar." (39)/ Okay, no need. Caca will go to a room
 CC : "Ndak mau" (selalu disertai tangis). (40)/ I don't want to (always crying)
 GG : "Ndak usah." (41)/ No need
 CC : "Ndak mau, ndak mau, ndak mau (menangis) ndak mauuuu" (menangis hingga terbatuk, si kakak tidak lagi menimpali, akhirnya si adik diam). (42)./ I don't want to, I don't want to, I do not want to (crying) I do not want to" (crying until he coughs, the older brother no longer responds, finally the younger sibling is silent)

Sibling bickering data analysis

Based on the sibling rivalry data above, it can be explained as follows. At the start of the conversation, GG asked what toy CC was holding; then CC answered what the toy was holding. In sentence (3), GG asks while grabbing the toy that CC is holding, so CC reacts with the negative word (4) does not want to (the reaction given by CC when GG does not want to hold the toy) because CC rejects it, GG finally says the negative word (5) no need (to prohibit CC from playing with him). Because he was not allowed to play with his sister GG, CC fought back by crying (6) while expressing his wish to continue playing with his sister GG. Feeling angry, GG emphasized that she did not want to let her sister play by repeating the negative word no to her CC (7). The same words and reactions were repeated in several sentences until MM asked what their problem was. GG explained sentences (12) and (17). However, because it was considered that GG's explanation did not match the facts, CC finally denied the explanation by saying the negative word, not (18), as a form of rejection. CC added the word unwillingly.

Not accepting her younger sister's rejection, GG emphasized it with the word "basically," followed by the negative word he does not want to. GG here does not want any rejection; his authority as an older brother is quite representative in sentence (19). CC still did not want to lose by emphasizing the word "do not want" for the umpteenth time with the added emotion of crying (20). In sentence (21), GG reiterates his desire to use the house toys, which are the source of their dispute; GG continues to use the main word for emphasis in this sentence. In sentence (22), CC protests her sister GG by using the negative word never to emphasize that she never uses the toy, meaning her sister continues to control the toy. However, in sentence (23), GG again uses the negative word "do not care" to stop the argument with his sister. However, something different was said in sentence (33). Even though there was a long debate in the previous few sentences, GG finally allowed her sister CC to play that day and gave the condition that she was not allowed to play the next day. CC, who did not accept the conditions proposed by her brother, filed a protest (34) while still using the negative word unwilling. Then, CC says a negative sentence in a sentence (36) by choosing the word no. Annoyed at not finding an agreement, GG finally forbade her sister from entering the room by choosing the negative word no need (39). However, CC did not accept it and continued using the word unwilling, expressing his emotions by crying (42).

Negative Words

The sibling rivalry data above found several negative words, including no, no, and no, with the following details. Negative words are not found in conversation (4) do not want to, (5) do not have to, (7) do not have to, (9) do not have to, (18) do not want to, (19) do not want to, (20) do not want to, (21) do not want to, (22) never, (23) do not care, (24) do not want to, (26) do not want to, (27) do not want to, (29) cannot, (33) cannot, (34) do not want to, (37) never, (39) do not have to, (40) do not want to, (41) don't have to, (42) don't want to. Apart from that, negative words were also found, consisting of the words do not have to (25), do not want to (36), do not play (34). Next, the negative word is not (31), and the negative word is not (18).

Emotional Engagement

Among the negative words found in the quarrel data, there was also involvement of negative emotions from siblings. The negative emotions often arise when sibling rivalry occurs: anger, crying, and screaming. Angry at the quarrel data above is described with an exclamation point (!) Crying is a common anger reaction when facing a situation that hurts or mentally debilitates someone. The benefit of crying when angry is to release emotions that help a person understand their feelings better (<https://health.kompas.com/page=all>). Shouting can also help regulate and control the hormone serotonin, which plays a role in controlling moods for the better. That way, the emotional feelings that explode will slowly improve (<https://kumpara.com/1yKjDqzA3t>).

4. Conclusion

The negative word forms found from the sibling rivalry data are not: the words do not want, do not have to, cannot, never, and do not care. Meanwhile, the word no consists of do not have to, do not want to, do not play; apart from that, there are also the words no and not. Meanwhile, the forms of emotional involvement in the sibling rivalry above are anger, crying, and shouting.

Acknowledgments

The research team would like to thank all parties who have contributed to the implementation of this research.

References

- Dhardjowidjojo, Soenjono. (2012). Psikolinguistik Pengantar Pemahaman Bahasa Manusia. Jakarta: Yayasan Pustaka Obor Indonesia.
- Bungin, Burhan. (2001). Metodologi Penelitian Sosial: Format-format Kuantitatif dan Kualitatif. Surabaya: Airlangga University Press.
- Mahsun. (2005). Metode Penelitian Bahasa. Jakarta: PT. Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Sudaryanto, (2015). Metode dan Teknik Analisis Bahasa: Pengantar Penelitian Wahana Kebudayaan secara Linguistis. Yogyakarta: Sanata Dharma University Press.
- Ulia, Ares. (2020). Dealing Kids Rivalry. Yogyakarta: Penerbit Briliant.
- <https://id.m.wikibooks.org>
- <https://health.kompas.com/page=all>
- <https://kumpara.com/1yKjDqzA3t>